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Mentoring in Kindergartens: Benefits for Newly Appointed Teachers, Mentors and Educational Organizations

Zacharoula Kontogianni¹, Efthymios Valkanos², Maria Sytziouki³, Iosif Fragoulis⁴, Marios Koutsoukos⁵

¹ Kindergarten teacher, M.Sc. Email: rkontogianni@gmail.com

² Professor, Department of Educational and Social Policy, University of Macedonia. Email: evalkan@uom.edu.gr

³ Assistant Professor, Department of Educational and Social Policy, University of Macedonia.

Email: sitziouki@uom.edu.gr

⁴ Professor ASPETE and Hellenic Open University. Email: sfaka@otenet.gr

⁵ Ass.Professor ASPETE and Hellenic Open University, Ph.D. Email: koutsoukos.marios@gmail.com

Abstract

This research aims to investigate the perceptions of kindergarten principals in the regional unit of Thessaloniki regarding the expected benefits for newly appointed teachers, mentors, and educational organizations. By conducting qualitative research, the perceptions of 15 kindergarten principals were explored using the research tool of semi-structured interviews. The interviews revealed that the heads of nursery schools identified, as the most important benefits for newly appointed teachers, the improvement of teaching methodology and the widening of the circle of social contacts through the cultivation of communication skills, as well as the understanding of the formal and informal culture of the educational organization. The supervisors themselves as mentors value key benefits the enrichment of knowledge and the renewal of teaching methods as a result of their interaction with their mentors as well as the improvement of communication skills. For educational organizations, the benefits seem to be linked to the benefits of the mentored and relate to the functioning of the organization as a learning community, the achievement of objectives, and the improvement of the quality of the work produced, while the improvement of communication levels works to the benefit of working relationships between the parties involved.

Keywords: Benefits, Educational Organization, Kindergarten Principals, Mentor, Mentoring, Mentoring, Newly Appointed Teacher

1. Introduction

Mentoring in the sense of guidance has historically been an integral part of human development. Gabel-Dunk & Craft (2004) state that the concept of mentoring is first encountered in Homer's *Odyssey*, as Mentor takes on the task of guiding, inspiring, and empowering Telemachus, the son of Odysseus.

Although mentoring has traditionally been widely known in the business world, the rapid and diverse developments that are reshaping the contemporary educational landscape have made the need for professional support for teachers and thus their participation in mentoring processes, internationally, imperative. The involvement of teachers in programs based on interaction, collaboration and initiation into reflective techniques, to solve problems and not exclusively the sterile provision of knowledge (Aspfors & Fransson, 2015) contributes

to the personal empowerment of teachers as well as to their professional development. In the field of education, much of the research focuses on mentoring and supporting newly appointed teachers (Ingersoll & Strong, 2011), while some research focuses on the function of mentoring as a process of strengthening the role of the school principal (Waterman & He, 2011). Still, other researchers focus on the link between mentoring and the retention of new teachers in education (Matthews, 2015).

Initially, the research interest was oriented toward mentors (Chao, Walz & Gardner, 1992) but then turned to both mentors and educational organizations (Ensher & Murhpy, 2011). Although, evaluating the effectiveness of mentoring involves difficulties due to the various factors associated with it, such for example the context of implementation or the achievement of goals (Allen, Eby, Poteet, Lentz, & Lima, 2004), results of several studies report benefits for all parties involved: mentor, mentee and educational organization (Clark & Byrnes, 2011; Hudson, 2013; Koutsoukos, 2021).

In Greece, the initial training of newly appointed teachers was initially institutionalized in 1985, while in 2010 the institution of the mentor was officially established for the first time by law, which was updated in 2021, linking the role of the mentor with the smooth adaptation and support of the newly appointed teacher. Both laws remained inapplicable, and the mentor institution was inactive. The current legislation refers to the introduction of a pedagogical advisor-mentor in formal primary and secondary education to guide, motivate and support newly appointed (up to 5 years of service) teachers.

The criteria for the selection of the mentor by the Ministry of Education, based on the current law, exclude the assignment of the role to the head teacher of the school unit, while the size of the schools defined by law as needing the institution, (six or more classrooms) exclude kindergartens from involvement in mentoring practices since they are all two- or one-room school units and the head teacher/headmistress of the kindergarten cannot assume the role of mentor.

Given the increased scientific interest in mentoring in the field of education, in combination with the current legislation that indirectly excludes kindergartens from the framework of the institution, the present research focuses its interest on investigating the perceptions of kindergarten supervisors regarding the benefits of mentoring for newly appointed teachers, the mentors themselves, and educational organizations.

2. Theoretical Framework- Benefits of mentoring in Education

2.1 Benefits of mentoring for newly appointed teachers

The literature on mentoring in education identifies benefits for mentors on multiple levels (Langdon, 2011; Peterson et al., 2010). Some of the most important benefits that research reports concerning mentors relate to improving teaching practices as well as strengthening critical thinking (Amram & Davidovitch, 2024; Kozelková, 2024; Koutsoukos et al., 2021; Koutsoukos & Sipitanou, 2020; Alabi & Allayande, 2017) by utilizing the feedback capacity (Ehrich et al., 2004).

The research of Phillips & Fragoulis (2010), Fragoulis & Valkanos (2011), as well as the research of Koutsoukos (2021), refer to an improvement in problem-solving ability at a professional level. Findings on the other hand, reported in Achinstein & Davis, (2014) research relate to the seamless adoption of student-centered teaching methods by teachers who participated in mentoring programs, compared to more traditional past models, while research by Vanderburg & Stephens (2010) and Peterson et al. (2010) find benefits in improving the productivity and effectiveness of mentored teachers.

The expansion of the network of personal and professional contacts as well as the improvement of communication skills is mentioned as another benefit for the mentors (Koutsoukos et al., 2021; Koutsoukos & Sipitanou, 2020; Phillips & Fragoulis, 2010; Ehrich et al., 2004).

Other research data support that the finding that appears with the highest frequency relates to the enhancement of self-confidence which is an additional benefit that mentors gain from their involvement in mentoring processes (Kozelková, 2024 · Amram & Davidovitch, 2024 · Trikas & Kasimatis, 2020 · Quintana, 2014 · Bowman, 2014 · Marable & Raimondi, 2007). It is also found that involvement in mentoring processes contributes to the strengthening of their self-confidence and contributes to the effective management of the problems they face, as it provides them with the possibility of beneficially managing the difficulties of their daily work life (Fragoulis & Valkanos, 2011 · Darwin & Palmer, 2009).

Research by Scandura & Williams (2004) showed a negative correlation of anxiety with the adoption of mentoring techniques, arguing that participation in mentoring processes affects reducing levels of anxiety in the professional field. In contrast, mentoring was found to be positively associated with job satisfaction and organizational commitment of mentored individuals (Amram & Davidovitch, 2024; Scandura & Williams, 2004). Research by Amram & Davidovitch (2024) and Achinstein & Athanases (2005) argue that mentoring contributes to the process of mentors' understanding of the culture of the educational organization. This is assisted by improving their levels of socialization in the workplace.

However, since 1980, when mentoring became part of the integration programs of newly appointed teachers (Hobson et al., 2009), a large number of studies have focused on the association of mentoring with the smooth adaptation and integration of newly appointed teachers (Trikas & Kasimatis, 2020; Ingersoll & Strong, 2011). Ingersoll and Strong (2011) in an attempt to conceptualize the term mentoring, conclude that it is a mentoring provided by veteran teachers to younger teachers. Similar reasoning linking mentoring to newly qualified teachers is also concluded by Phillips & Fragoulis (2010) who argue that mentors may provide guidance to improve the teaching weaknesses of their mentees through the implementation of innovative teaching practices.

In a recent survey by Dalmatsou & Lazarakou (2024) of newly appointed teachers on peer mentoring, it is reported that the majority of newly appointed teachers consider the institution of peer mentoring to be a peer mentor with prerequisites of close age between mentor and mentee as well as hierarchical equality, would provide them with a benefit in terms of managing professional difficulties as it would direct the feelings of anxiety they experience in the early years of their careers. Similar findings seem to be reported in the research of Morettini et al. (2020), who argue that participation in mentoring processes acts helpfully in various fields, given the pervasive levels of occupational anxiety in the educational field.

Given that the professional development of newly qualified teachers in terms of knowledge acquisition and skill cultivation is an important pillar of learning outcomes (Darling-Hammond, 2006), the literature acknowledges the value of mentoring in preventing attrition among newly qualified teachers (Hobson et al., 2009).

Other research findings suggest that mentoring improves the new teacher's ability to commit to providing quality instruction to their students, and contributes to the use of effective teaching practices, while also contributing to improved student achievement (Ingersoll & Strong, 2011).

Duse, Duse, & Karkowska (2017) state that participation in mentoring processes for newly appointed teachers is an important field of professional action as it aims to keep new teachers in the field of education, due to dissatisfaction caused mainly by economic factors, there is a phenomenon of massive departures from educational organizations, internationally.

The derivation of professional satisfaction of newly appointed teachers from their involvement in mentoring processes is mentioned as a finding in a study by Spanorriga, Tsiotakis, & Jimoyiannis (2018), while according to Trika & Kasimatis (2020), participation in mentoring processes helps the smooth integration of the newly appointed teacher in the school unit as it also contributes to his/her psychological, emotional, didactic and administrative support. Similar conclusions are confirmed by studies by Killion (2009) and Knight (2007). Moreover, participation in mentoring processes helps new teachers in their socialization process (Sinclair, 2003). In a recent study of novice teacher mentors in Israel, Amram & Davidovitch (2024) argue that engaging novice teachers in mentoring processes improves teaching practices, provides assistance in classroom management,

student assessment, professional identity development, stimulates a sense of efficacy, and has an improving effect on fostering relationships with students, while contributing to the retention of new teachers in the profession.

Makropoulou & Iordanidis (2016) in their research regarding the expected benefits of newly appointed teachers from the mentoring institution argue that newly appointed teachers are expected to experience rapid professional development and improvement in their communication skills along with the development of their sense of self-confidence.

The benefits of mentoring for newly appointed teachers according to Alabi & Allayande (2017) are identified in the encouragement of newly appointed teachers and the creation of an attractive model of teaching activity, factors that may contribute to the retention of newly appointed teachers in the educational field.

2.2 Benefits of mentoring for mentors

The benefits of mentoring for mentors are related to the reciprocity of the mentoring relationship as well as its interactive nature (Jacobi, 1991). One of the most important benefits that mentors gain from engaging in mentoring processes is the improvement of their communication skills (Philips & Fragoulis, 2010) and the cultivation of an active listening factor that enables them to detect more effectively the needs of the mentored teachers (Philips & Fragoulis, 2010; Lopez-Real & Kwan, 2005). Moreover, it creates new support networks with other professionals in the field through collaboration (Koutsoukos & Sipitanou, 2020; Philips & Fragoulis, 2010; Ehrich et al., 2004).

Another notable benefit for mentors is the positive impact that mentoring has on their own personal and professional development (Lopez-Real & Kwan, 2005; Ehrich et al., 2004; Allen & Eby, 2003), while according to research by Koutsoukos, Fragoulis, Valkanos, Kyriatzakou (2021) the main benefit that mentors themselves gain from their participation in mentoring processes is continuous self-improvement, a finding that was also verified by the comparative study by Clarke, & Mena, (2020) with mentors from six countries.

Hudson (2013) points to the development of mentors' pedagogical practices as a benefit, while Amram & Davidovitch, (2024) and Mc Connell & Geesa, (2019) cite the mentors' reflection as a benefit, a process that redefines their perceptions regarding their teaching work and contributes to the cultivation of teaching skills. Still, scholars in the field, cite the development of leadership skills as a benefit for mentors (Hansford, Tennent & Ehrich, 2003).

The sharing of ideas and the enrichment of the mentors' knowledge through collaborative interaction with the mentors, who are a source of new ideas for them (Ehrich et al., 2004), is mentioned in the literature as an additional benefit that mentors gain. Moreover, interaction with mentors contributes to the renegotiation of the mentors' teaching mindset (Philips & Fragoulis, 2010), with Hobson et al. (2009) and Koutsoukos (2021) referring to a revitalization of their teaching willingness.

The benefits of mentoring for the mentors themselves still include the enhancement of their sense of personal satisfaction (Amram & Davidovitch, 2024; Shapira-Lishchinsky, 2012; Ehrich et al., 2004; Allen & Eby, 2003) with Allen & Eby (2003) arguing that the benefits of informal mentoring are greater. Kram (1985) on the other hand, finds that mentors' satisfaction is enhanced through reflecting themselves in the personalities of their mentors.

The feeling of usefulness that comes from providing knowledge and experiences to the mentors (Hansman, 2002; Kennett & Lomas, 2015) as well as the enhancement of the mentor's self-confidence (Louca & Petsiou, 2016) are mentioned in the literature as important benefits for mentors.

Simpson et al. (2007), on the other hand, point out that mentors, through the process of "self-reflection," learn themselves through the objects of input and discussion with their mentors, which helps not only to identify their strengths and weaknesses but also to improve their teaching behavior (Hobson et al., 2009).

2.3 Benefits of mentoring for the educational organization

According to the literature review, participation in mentoring processes is associated with multiple benefits for all parties involved, mentor, mentee, mentor and educational organization (Lavin Colky & Young, 2006). The benefits gained by the educational organization from mentoring positively correlate the benefits of the mentored and at the same time are linked to the concept of the learning organization (Koutsoukos, 2021). A learning organization is considered an organization that through a learning process, at the individual and collective level (Retna & TeeNg, 2016), is constantly driven to change (Watkins & Marsick, 1996). According to Schechter (2008), the adoption of innovative processes that promote teachers' professional development is another element of the learning organization concept. Through this perspective, mentoring as an innovative process of knowledge provision contributes to the transformation of the educational organization into a learning organization (Koutsoukos & Sipitanou, 2020).

The benefits that the organization gains by utilizing mentoring practices are the following:

Cultivating a learning culture and developing lifelong learning. The educational organization that participates in mentoring processes leverages learning by engaging the entire educational community as through the formation of a reflective culture, it strengthens the spirit of lifelong learning and contributes to the promotion of innovative actions (Kozelková, 2024; Koutsoukos & Sipitanou, 2020; Cosner & Jones, 2016; OECD, 2016; Orland-Barak, 2005; Hargreaves & Fullan, 2000).

As collaborative relationships develop and the members involved gain feelings of satisfaction, conditions for higher quality social contact between the network of the educational community are fostered. At the same time, a willingness to seek help on issues related to their personal and professional development is diffused to other educational organization members (Phillips & Fragoulis, 2010; Moor et al., 2005).

Collaborative culture, as another benefit for the educational organization, is built through the application of techniques such as mentor support, learning networks, and discussion circles (Koutsoukos, 2021; Koutsoukos & Sipitanou, 2020; Cosner & Jones, 2016; OECD, 2016; Anastasiou, Valkanos, Fragoulis & Androutsou, 2015).

The literature, as an additional benefit that the educational organization gains from the participation of its members in mentoring processes, recognizes the retention of teachers in the educational organization and the reduction of new teacher departures (Schwan, Wold, Moon, Neville, & Outka, 2020; Banks, Conway, Darmody, Leavy, Smyth & Watson, 2015; Bowman, 2014). However, the use of mentoring also contributes to the achievement of the organization's goals and thus increases its effectiveness (Koutsoukos et al., 2021; Frangoulis & Valkanos, 2011; Roberts, 2000). At the same time, findings from the research of Koutsoukos & Sipitanou (2020) also speak of an increase in employee productivity.

Table 1: Mentoring: indicative benefits for all parties involved

s	Benefits for mentors	Benefits for the educational organization
Smooth adaptation and integration into the educational organisation	Improving communication skills	Cultivating a learning culture and developing lifelong learning
Managing professional difficulties	Development of cooperation networks	Creating a collaborative culture
Improving teaching practices	Personal and professional development	Promotion of innovative actions
Wear prevention	Development of new optics	Reduction of resignations
Conservation in the educational area	Enhancing feelings of satisfaction	Achieving goals
Job satisfaction	Self confidence	Increasing productivity
Improved communication skills/ Self-confidence		

3. Research design

This was an empirical study that investigate the perceptions of kindergarten principals in the regional unit of Thessaloniki regarding the expected benefits for newly appointed teachers, mentors, and educational organizations. By conducting qualitative research, the perceptions of 15 kindergarten principals were explored using the research tool of semi-structured interviews.

4. Research questions

The research questions to which the research sought answers are the following:

1. What are the views of kindergarten principals on the benefits of newly appointed teachers?
2. What are the views of kindergarten principals on the benefits they derive as mentors from the mentoring relationship?
3. What are the views of kindergarten principals on the benefits that the educational organization derives from the mentoring process as themselves?

5. Research Methodology

5.1 Sample and Participants

For the research needs, a sample of 15 heads of kindergartens in the regional unit of Thessaloniki was selected. The sampling, for reasons that serve the research process practically, was done without probability because the participants in the survey meet the required characteristics. Still, their selection was done for easy access and willingness of these kindergarten principals to participate in the survey. Consequently, the survey sample is a convenience sample (Creswell, 2011). Specifically, the snowball technique was followed as the sample was formed through the process of accumulation (Isari & Pourkos, 2015).

The participants were all women. As shown in Table 2 regarding the age distribution of the participants during the survey period, the average age of the participants was 51.2 years. Regarding the educational level of the participants, out of the total of 15 kindergarten heads, 9 (60%) held a postgraduate degree and 6 (40%) held an HEI degree. In terms of years of teaching experience, the average is 23.5 years of teaching experience. Regarding the participants' administrative experience, the average number of years of administrative experience is 12.1 years.

Table 2: Profile of interview participants

	Age	Level of studies	Teaching experience (years)	Administrative experience (years)
S1	56	University degree	25	15
S2	57	University degree	29	15
S3	40	Postgraduate degree	15	4
S4	55	University degree	31	29
S5	38	Postgraduate degree	12	3
S6	56	Postgraduate degree	26	18
S7	45	Postgraduate degree	21	4
S8	39	Postgraduate degree	10	4
S9	60	University degree	37	20
S10	56	University degree	23	17
S11	50	Postgraduate degree	18	14
S12	55	Postgraduate degree	28	12
S13	50	Postgraduate degree	25	9
S14	59	University degree	25	2

S15	52	Postgraduate degree	28	16
Average (years)	51.2	6 University Degree 9 Postgraduate Degree	23.5	12.1

5.2 Data collection - Research instrument

For the data collection, the qualitative research method was chosen as it was considered more suitable since it allowed capturing the views in a free context, while at the same time it provided the opportunity to interpret and deepen the perceptions of the participants (Tsiolis, 2014). The semi-structured interview was chosen as a research tool due to its flexible nature and the possibility of deepening the issues under investigation (Isari & Pourkos, 2015). To create the interview guide, questions were formulated based on previous, related research. In total, 15 semi-structured interviews were conducted remotely using the Google Meet platform, each lasting approximately 20-30 minutes. The interviews were conducted between November and December 2023.

5.3 Data procedure

The qualitative content analysis method was used to process the data, specifically thematic analysis. The interview questions were sorted based on the research questions. The extraction of the themes that emerged during the transcription of the interviews answered the research questions, and a pilot interview was conducted to carry out the final interview design.

6. Results

Regarding the first research question on the benefits that newly appointed teachers gain from the use of mentoring (Table 3), the answers of the head teachers of kindergartens were dominated by the improvement of the methods and teaching practices of the newly appointed teachers, the expansion of the circle of social contacts as well as the development of the communication skills of the newly appointed teachers. Several respondents reflect in their answers benefits in terms of understanding the formal and informal parts of the culture of the educational organization.

Table 3: Key benefits of mentoring for newly appointed teachers

Benefits for newly appointed teachers	Number of answers	Percentage
Improving teaching methods and practices	14/15	93.3%
Broadening the circle of social contacts and developing communication skills	14/15	93,3%
Understanding the formal and informal part of the culture of the educational organization	12/15	80%

Regarding the second research question related to the benefits that kindergarten supervisors themselves gain as mentors, (Table 4) the enrichment of knowledge and renewal of mentors concerning teaching through interaction with the mentored dominated the respondents' answers. Many responses also focus on the benefit gained by mentors in terms of improving their communication skills and expanding their network of social contacts. Of particular interest are also the responses related to the personal satisfaction that mentors derive from the feeling of giving back concerning the development process of their mentees. Again, several responses advocate benefits related to the mentor's professional and personal development.

Table 4: Key benefits of mentoring for mentors

Benefits for mentors	Number of answers	Percentage
Enriching the knowledge and renewal of mentors concerning teaching through interaction with mentors	15/15	100%
Improving communication skills and widening social contacts	15/15	100%
Personal satisfaction	12/15	80%
Professional and personal development	11/15	73.3%

Regarding the benefits gained by the educational organization by utilizing mentoring practices (Table 5), the majority of the participants preferred in their responses the positive association of mentoring with the learning organization, while at the same time, they linked the benefits of mentoring for the educational organization with the benefits of mentoring for the mentored.

Increasing the efficiency of the organisation as well as improving the quality of the work produced dominate as benefits for the learning organisation, while a large proportion of respondents focus in their answers on improving communication and working relationships. These benefits (increasing the effectiveness of the organisation/improving the quality of the work produced/improving communication and working relations) are according to the participants' answers and the related benefits, guided and educational organization.

Table 5: Key benefits of mentoring for the educational organization

Benefits for the educational organization	Number of answers	Percentage
Operation of the organization as a learning community	15/15	100%
Positive correlation between the benefits of mentoring for the educational organization and the benefits of mentoring for the mentored	15/15	100%
Increasing efficiency	15/15	100%
Improving the quality of the work produced	15/15	100%
Improving communication and working relations	13/15	86.6%

7. Discussion

From the results regarding the first research question, it appeared that one of the main benefits for the newly appointed teachers, according to the kindergarten heads, is the improvement of teaching methods and practices. This finding is confirmed by findings of other studies by Amram & Davidovitch (2024), Trika & Kasimatis (2020), Alambi & Alayande (2017), Ingersoll & Strong (2011) and Certo, (2005) who found that engaging newly qualified teachers in effective mentoring processes is an important tool for improving their teaching practices.

An equally significant proportion of kindergarten heads mention the benefits of newly appointed teachers in terms of expanding their network of social contacts and cultivating their communication skills. These findings are confirmed by research results from Karampassi & Papanis (2019), Huffman (2017), Banks et al. (2015), Phillips & Fragoulis (2010), Ehrich et al. (2004) and Sinclair (2003). Of particular interest is the research finding regarding the understanding of the culture of the educational organization concerning its formal and informal functioning. This finding converges with the findings of Huffman's (2017) qualitative research in the U.S. and findings of Achinstein & Athanases (2005). These findings may be justified since according to research by Kutsyuruba et al. (2019), Alabi et al. (2017), and Hobson, & Malderez (2013) a wide range of newly appointed teachers' needs focus on issues such as classroom management, familiarization with school facilities and equipment, relationship building, student assessment, and teaching effectiveness.

In the findings of the research, with regard to the second research question, benefits are found regarding the enrichment of mentors' knowledge and their didactic renewal through interaction with the mentored (Koutsoukos,

2021; Petrovska et al., 2018; Philips & Fragoulis, 2010; Ehrich et al., 2004; Hargreaves & Fullan, 2000) confirming the constructivist model of mentoring (Hargreaves & Fullan, 2000). The views of the research participants can be interpreted if we consider that the role of the mentor is linked to the teachers' own teaching (Koutsoukos, 2021). Another interpretation of these views can possibly be the fact that the mentor through the interaction with the mentee reshapes his/her methods and teaching behavior (Philips & Fragoulis, 2010). Besides, according to Jacobi (1991), the benefits of mentoring concern both the mentor and the mentee since it is an interactional relationship. An interesting finding is the improvement of the mentor's communication skills through the use of mentoring techniques (Hobson et al., 2020; Philips & Fragoulis, 2010) and the gaining of a sense of personal satisfaction from his/her contribution to the mentor's development (Amram & Davidovitch, 2024; Papadimitriou, 2023; Shapira-Lishchinsky, 2012; Ehrich et al., 2004; Allen & Eby, 2003). The views of kindergarten supervisors are interpreted if we consider that mentors improve their skills, develop their sense of self-esteem, and increase their levels of personal development through the support they provide to their mentors (Michiotis et al., 2006). The cultivation of communication skills, on the other hand, is considered an essential characteristic of the mentor (Koutsoukos, 2021; Mee-Lee & Bush, 2003; Good, Halpin & Halpin, 2000), as the ability to express oneself clearly and understandably is considered necessary (Ehrich et al., 2004), while communication skills are considered necessary for the psychological support of the mentored (Kapachtsi, 2020).

The ongoing personal and professional development of the mentor (Papadimitriou, 2023; Ponte & Twomey, 2014; Lopez-Real & Kwan, 2005; Ehrich et al., 2004; Allen & Eby, 2003) is mentioned as another benefit of the mentoring process. The views expressed by the participants are interpreted if we consider that within the mentoring process, professional growth and development of the mentored is achieved as the mentor according to Clutterbuck (2005) manages the relationship, encourages, feeds safely and consistently, teaches and responds to the needs of the mentored.

Regarding the third research question, the research findings indicate that the benefits that the educational organization derives from mentoring are related to the benefits that the mentored individuals derive (Koutsoukos & Sipitanou, 2020; Dimos and Papagiyanopoulou, 2017) as well as the concept of a learning organization (Hobson et al, 2020 · Cosner & Jones, 2016; OECD, 2016; Orland-Barak, 2005 · Hargreaves & Fullan, 2000). The link between the benefits of mentoring and the benefits of the learning organization is interpreted when considering the association of mentoring with the diffusion of a collaborative culture and seeking help from other members of the organization (Phillips & Fragoulis, 2010; Moor et al., 2005). In this light, mentoring also contributes to the transformation of the organization into a learning organization, since it acts as a knowledge provider to its members (Koutsoukos & Sipitanou, 2020).

The findings of the present research indicate benefits for the educational organization in terms of improving its efficiency levels (Koutsoukos et al., 2021; Koutsoukos & Sipitanou, 2020; Fragoulis & Valkanos, 2011; Michiotis et al., 2006; Roberts, 2000) and improving the quality of the work produced. This finding converges with similar research findings of Koutsoukos & Sipitanou (2020) and Colky & Young (2007). These findings can be interpreted if one considers that the cultivation of knowledge and skills works for the benefit of the organization and increases its effectiveness levels through the achievement of its goals (Fragoulis & Valkanos, 2011; Roberts, 2000).

The finding regarding the improvement of communication levels between members of the educational organization and the improvement of working relationships converges with the findings of the research of Koutsoukos & Sipitanou, (2020) and can be interpreted if one considers that mentoring promotes the collaborative culture of the members of the educational organization (Fragoulis & Valkanos, 2011) and strengthens the relationships between them (Moor et al., 2005).

8. Conclusion

In conclusion, based on the results of the survey, it seems that kindergarten principals in the regional unit of Thessaloniki, report benefits for all parties involved, new teacher, mentor and educational organization. For the newly appointed teachers the benefits are related to the improvement of teaching methods, the cultivation of communication skills and the understanding of the formal and informal culture of the educational organization.

The benefits of mentors coincide with the benefits of mentored teachers and focus on improving teaching methodology techniques and developing communication skills through an interactional relationship. For the training organization the benefits coincide with the benefits of the mentors as the mentoring process is positively related to the concept of the mentoring organization and focus on improving the effectiveness of the organization, the quality of the work produced, and the development of working relationships.

The findings of this research can be complemented by future research attempts that will include quantitative and qualitative measurements of kindergarten principals to make the sample more representative in terms of range and geographical area (national scale). Conducting a mixed survey of both head teachers of kindergartens and newly appointed teachers. Carrying out a field survey using the observation method with preschool heads. Repeating a qualitative survey only among heads of private kindergartens.

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